

NUMERICAL MODELING FOR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF Namd™ CFRP

S. Tomita^{1*}, J. Koyanagi², T. Komukai³, T. Uno⁴

¹ Department of Materials Science and Technology, Graduate School of Tokyo University of Science, Tokyo, Japan, 8218551@ed.tus.ac.jp

² Department of Materials Science and Technology, Tokyo University of Science, Tokyo, Japan

³ NITTA CORPORATION, Nara, Japan

⁴ YONEX CO., LTD., Niigata, Japan

Keywords: Namd™, CFRP, CNT, FEM, Collision analysis

ABSTRACT

In this study, we compared carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) and Namd™ CFRP (CFRP which includes carbon nanotube (CNT), and it was developed by NITTA CORPORATION [1]). The commercial finite element analysis (FEA) software Abaqus was used for the analysis. In the analysis, we conducted collision simulation using conventional CFRP laminate and Namd™ CFRP laminate model. We expressed the ply crack by Hashin damage theory and express the delamination by cohesive contact. In collision analysis, impactor collided with Namd™ CFRP laminate and conventional CFRP laminate, and we compared the delamination and cracks in each layer of laminate. Comparing Namd™ CFRP and conventional CFRP, the laminate of Namd™ CFRP was less damaged than the laminate of conventional CFRP. The simulated results showed that impact damage resistance is improved by CNT.

1 INTRODUCTION

Namd™ CFRP (CFRP containing CNT) was developed by NITTA CORPORATION [1]. As shown in an electron microscopic image of carbon fiber constituting Namd™ CFRP (Fig. 1), the CNTs form a mesh structure layer on the surface of carbon fiber. When comparing Namd™ CFRP with conventional CFRP, various mechanical properties differences were reported in these composite materials. Speed dependency of Namd™ CFRP is smaller than that of conventional CFRP. Interlaminar toughness of Namd™ CFRP laminates is about 30% greater than that of conventional CFRP laminate. Damping ratio of Namd™ CFRP is greater than that of conventional CFRP. In this study, we focused on improving the interlaminar toughness. Since conventional CFRP laminate has low interlaminar toughness, delamination occurs easily by out-of-plane impact load. Therefore, evaluation of impact resistance is important when using CFRP laminate in a structure, because delamination reduces the mechanical properties of the material. Because it is difficult to accurately

Fig. 1 An electron microscopic image of the fibers constituting Namd™ CFRP.

observe the damage inside the laminate in collision experiments, we conducted collision analysis using FEM that can predict the damage inside the laminate. In collision analysis, impactor collides with Namd™ CFRP and conventional CFRP laminates and compare the delamination and cracking of each laminate. The stacking order of laminates is $[0/90]_8$. In the analysis, we expressed delamination using cohesive contact which considers failure conditions in mixed mode. In order to consider anisotropy of Namd™ CFRP and conventional CFRP, we apply the anisotropic damage model based on the Hashin damage theory.

2 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

2.1 MODEL OF COLLISION ANALYSIS

We conduct the collision analysis and investigated the damage of Namd™ CFRP and conventional CFRP laminates. In this simulation, we adapt the dynamic analysis and damage extension was simulated. Fig. 2 shows condition of collision analysis. The dimensions of laminate are 60 mm square and 1.8 mm thick. The stacking order of laminates is $[0/90]_8$. Each layer is divided by the four nodes continuum shell element. As shown in Fig. 2, the laminate is simply supported by the support block containing a 50 mm diameter circular hole at the centre. The support block is expressed as rigid body and it fixed. The dimensions of impactor are 30 mm in diameter and 85 mm in length. The total mass of the impactor is 450 g. The impactor is expressed as rigid body. Initial speed of impactor is -2.62 m/s in the z direction. Fig. 3 shows the finite element models of laminates and base. Fig. 4 shows the finite element model of impactor. Because of symmetry, one quarter of the structure is modelled in order to reduce computational costs. We apply the anisotropic damage model based on the Hashin damage theory to laminate model in order to express ply crack. To consider the delamination, cohesive contact with mixed-mode traction-separation law (Fig. 5) is introduced between the layers.

Fig. 2 Condition of collision analysis.

Fig. 3 Finite element models of laminates and base.

Fig. 4 Finite element model of impactor.

2.2 HASHIN DAMAGE THEORY

In the collision analysis, the damage initiation criterion based on Hashin damage theory is applied to laminates [2]. Hashin damage theory considered four failure mode shown in Equation (1) ~ (4),
Tensile fiber mode

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{\sigma_A^+}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{\tau_A}\right)^2 = 1 \quad \sigma_{11} > 0 \quad (1)$$

Fiber compressive mode

$$\sigma_{11} = -\sigma_A^- \quad \sigma_{11} < 0 \quad (2)$$

Tensile matrix mode

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{\sigma_T^+}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{\tau_A}\right)^2 = 1 \quad \sigma_{22} > 0 \quad (3)$$

Compressive matrix mode

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2\tau_T}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_T^-}{2\tau_T}\right)^2 - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_{22}}{\sigma_T^-} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{\tau_A}\right)^2 = 1 \quad \sigma_{22} < 0 \quad (4)$$

2.3 COHESIVE CONTACT THEORY

We introduced cohesive contact to ply-ply interface in order to express delamination of laminate. Fig. 5 shows the cohesive contact with mixed-mode traction-separation law [3]. Cohesive contact doesn't consider thickness. Y_n is the pure tensile strength and Y_s is the pure shear strength. t_n and t_s are contact tensile and shear stress components obtained by applying elastic force-separation behavior to the separation amount assuming no damage. G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are the critical energy release rate for each deformation mode. G_c is the critical energy release rate under mixed mode and determines the progress of delamination. When traction force become zero, failure in mix mode (ply-ply interfacial delamination) is occurred.

Fig. 5 Traction-separation law for cohesive behavior under mixed-mode.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.2 RESULTS OF COLLISION ANALYSIS

Fig. 6 shows the delamination of each layer of conventional CFRP after impact. Fig. 7 shows the delamination of each layer of Namd™ CFRP after impact. In Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, white area shows ply crack and red area shows delamination. Comparing Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, conventional CFRP has more delamination area than Namd™ CFRP. As shown in Fig. 7, ply3~5 of Namd™ CFRP laminate have no damage. But there is almost no difference in the size of the cracks comparing conventional CFRP and Namd™ CFRP. From Fig. 6, delamination of conventional CFRP laminate expands along the ply crack. But delamination of Namd™ CFRP doesn't expand along ply crack. The difference between conventional CFRP laminate and Namd™ CFRP laminate is only the presence or absence of CNT. So, we think that CNT of Namd™ CFRP strengthen layer-layer interface.

Fig. 6 The delamination of each layer of conventional CFRP.

Fig. 7 The delamination of each layer of Namd™ CFRP.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we predicted the damage inside the laminates of conventional CFRP and Namd™ CFRP. We created a finite element model of laminates and conducted collision analysis. We applied the anisotropic damage model based on the Hashin damage theory to laminate model in order to express ply crack. And, cohesive contact with mixed-mode traction-separation law was introduced between the layers to consider the delamination. We researched amount of crack and delamination of each laminate using collision analysis. In collision analysis, Namd™ CFRP had less delamination area than conventional CFRP. The difference between conventional CFRP laminate and Namd™ CFRP laminate is only the presence or absence of CNT. So, we thought that CNT of Namd™ CFRP strengthen ply-ply interface.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work supported by T. Komukai (NITTA CORPORATION) and T. Uno (YONEX CO., LTD).

REFERENCES

- [1] NITTA CORPORATION https://www.nitta.co.jp/new_technology/#sec01.
- [2] Hashin Z. 1980. "Failure Criteria for Unidirectional Fiber Composites," *Journal of Applied Mechanics.*, 47:329-334.
- [3] J. Koyanagi, P.D. Shah, S. Kimura, S.K. Ha, H. Kawada, Mixed-mode interfacial debonding simulation in single-fiber composite under a transverse load, *J Solid Mech Mater Eng.*, 3:796–806, 2009.